

Oceanic Iodine, Wind Direction

And Countries Severely Affected By COVID-19 Mortality

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The United States, Mexico, India, Brazil, the United Kingdom, and continental Europe are unfortunately experiencing the highest rates of SARS-Cov-2 mortality. These countries are right next to the hotspots of iodine release in the oceans. In terms of the prevailing wind directions on Earth, we find that there is strong evidence for the "geographical coincidence" of "Oceanic Iodine Hotspots", and the "SARS-Cov-2 mortality Hotspots."

We have already seen wind time-dependent time trends for SARS-Cov-2 intensification in Europe, Asia, and also within Iran (both temporal and directional) [2] [3]. These three types of evidence (geographical, temporal, and directional) suggest that the main cause of the corona's rise and fall in different regions is the "released oceanic iodine" reaching different areas by wind (Interestingly, iodine is also carried by aerosol particles, which our face-masks can absorb and prevent their inhalation). The finding itself (relation between oceanic iodine and SARS-Cov-2 hotspots) suggests that part of the SARS-COV-2 multisystem syndrome is due to hormonal or allergic reactions to inhaled iodine, which pave the way for the COVID-19 virus to flourish further in the body.

The solution can be anti-iodine modulators whose effect on the body on thyroid hormones [4] is the opposite of the effect of excess iodine (such as Trigonelline, coffee, Bell pepper, turmeric, ginger, etc.). Therefore, these body of evidences suggests that Trigonelline can be a drug for the prevention and treatment of this syndrome, in this way. And God knows.

More than six clinical and metabolomics studies in the United States, China, Germany, France, and the United Kingdom [5] have shown the effect of Trigonelline levels in the blood as a prognosis of non-deterioration and deterioration in SARS-Cov-2 patients: those with higher Trigonelline levels in the blood, Their condition has not worsened. Trigonelline is found in fenugreek seeds, coffee, especially Arabic, bell peppers, etc.

Thanks & Regards

Resources

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